

Economic Cost of Vision Loss for Inclusive Development: The Direct and Indirect Perspectives

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
26 August 2025

ABSTRACT

The study assesses the direct and indirect economic burden arising from cataract-related blindness in Borno State. A survey method using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was conducted to collect data, and a cluster random sampling technique was employed to select 1161 cataract vision-impaired patients. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. The results revealed that all indicators of direct economic burden (amount incurred for diagnoses/laboratory tests, monthly expenditure on treatment/drug, amount spent on cataract surgery, as well as the amount spent per month on transportation to the hospital) and indirect productivity cost (frequency of hospital visits for follow-ups, man hour(s) loss in each visit to see the eye Doctor, ability to participate in the labour force, and other intangible costs associated with the cataract vision impairment) arising from cataract vision impairment were significantly associated with the number of years with impairment. The implication of this finding is that the productivity and income of the surveyed participants are affected by the economic burden arising from cataract vision impairment. The results provide a compelling case for policymakers, healthcare providers, and development stakeholders to prioritize cataract prevention and treatment as a critical component of public health strategies in Borno State. Integrating the economic perspective into healthcare planning will enable stakeholders to design targeted interventions that not only restore vision but also enhance economic productivity and reduce the cycle of poverty.

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KEYWORDS: cataract, economic loss, sustainability, vision impairment,

INTRODUCTION

Cataract is one of the leading causes of blindness worldwide. It is projected to affect about 52.6 million people globally. Cataract has led to a significant public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income regions of African countries. As indicated by Mohamed et al. (2024), more than 6 million people are suffering from cataract-related vision impairments. In Nigeria, particularly in Borno State, located in the northeastern part of the country, cataract-related vision impairment has profound social and economic consequences. The condition not only limits individuals' ability to perform daily tasks but also significantly reduces productivity, contributing to poverty and dependency within households. Studies have shown that vision impairment caused by cataract disproportionately affects vulnerable populations, such as the

elderly and those in rural areas, who often lack access to timely surgical interventions and adequate healthcare services (Resnikoff et al., 2021). This highlights the need for targeted interventions to mitigate the economic and social impacts of cataract-related blindness in states like Borno State.

The economic burden arising from cataract vision impairment in Borno State can be categorized into direct and indirect monetary losses. Direct costs include expenses incurred for healthcare services, such as consultations, surgeries, medications, and transportation to treatment centers. Indirect costs, on the other hand, arise from reduced productivity, lost income, and the opportunity costs borne by caregivers who must provide support to affected individuals. These financial losses extend beyond individual households to impact the

broader economy, aggravating the cycle of poverty and limiting sustainable development. Understanding and quantifying these losses is essential for policymakers to design effective public health strategies and allocate resources toward cataract prevention and treatment programs (Frick et al., 2015).

Cataract-induced vision impairment is a significant public health concern in Borno State. Recent studies indicate that over 55% of preventable blindness cases in the state are attributed to cataracts. This high prevalence not only diminishes the quality of life for affected individuals but also imposes substantial economic burdens on households and the broader community. The economic impact of cataract-related vision impairment encompasses both direct and indirect costs. Direct costs involve medical expenses for treatments and surgeries, while indirect costs include productivity losses and the opportunity costs borne by caregivers. A study focusing on Borno State revealed that approximately 62.1% of surveyed participants suffered from cataract vision impairment, highlighting the extent of this issue (Frick et al., 2015). Addressing this challenge is crucial for enhancing individual well-being and promoting sustainable economic development in the region.

Despite the growing burden of cataract-related vision impairment in the State, there remains a significant gap in the understanding and quantification of its economic impact. Existing studies on the economic consequences of cataracts in Nigeria often focus on national or regional estimates, leaving state-specific studies (see Bello et al., 2024; Singh and Mohanty, 2024; Mahomed et al, 2024; Kyei et al., 2024; Mannava et al., 2022). Additionally, most studies emphasize the clinical and epidemiological aspects of cataracts without adequately exploring the financial burden borne by affected individuals, households, and the broader economy (see Rabiou et al., 2023; Adio and Onua, 2023; Taryam, 2020). This lack of grassroots and comprehensive data hinders the ability of policymakers to design and implement targeted interventions tailored to the unique socioeconomic context of Borno State. This study aims to address these gaps by providing a detailed analysis of the direct and indirect monetary losses arising from cataract-related vision impairment in Borno State. By quantifying the financial burden, including healthcare costs, productivity losses, and opportunity costs for caregivers, the research will offer valuable insights into the economic dimensions of cataract-induced vision loss. The findings will serve as a critical resource for policymakers, healthcare providers, and development agencies in prioritizing resource allocation, designing public health interventions, and advocating for sustainable development strategies to mitigate the economic and social impacts of cataract vision impairment in Borno State.

METHODOLOGY

The study location

The study area Borno State, is located in the northeastern geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Its geographical coordinates are $11^{\circ}30'N$ and $13^{\circ}00'E$. According to 2006 National Population and Housing Census, the population of Borno was 4,171,104 (NPC, 2006). The State is bordered by Yobe state to the west, Adamawa to the south, Gombe to the southwest. In terms of nation border, it is the only Nigerian state that has border with three foreign countries. It is bordered with Cameroon to the east, Niger to the north and Chad to the northeast. Furthermore, Borno is one of the largest states in Nigeria. It is subdivided into 27 local government areas, each with its own administrative headquarters. Politically, the state is divided into three senatorial zones (Borno Central, Borno North, and Borno South) with 9 local government areas in each zone.

The population of the study mainly consists of cataract visually impaired people in Borno state. Cataracts are more prevalent in people aged 40 years and above. This population of respondents is expected to be obtained from patients that receive treatment in the state eye medical centers and clinics; identification of cataract vision-impaired persons by community leaders and referrals. The identified or referred impaired persons mostly have evidence of diagnosis and follow-up on cataract vision impairment.

Method of data collection

To collect the samples from the impaired people of the state, a structured questionnaire was used as the instrument of data collection. A questionnaire offers a structured and measurable way to collect data on issues, making it easier to analyze and draw conclusions from survey responses. Thus, the questionnaire was designed into four sections, namely demographic information, direct medical expenditure, non-direct medical expenditure, and indirect productivity costs. The questionnaire was translated into the native language and reverted by an expert before being transferred into online data collection kits (ODK Collect/Kobo Collect) software on an Android phone to enable data collection monitoring. The principal and co-researcher trained research assistants to assist in the data collection process. We ensure that the research assistants are fluent in both English and the native language to be able to detect biased responses. A pilot survey was first carried out in Maiduguri, which is the state capital, and all observations were corrected before embarking on main data collection. Furthermore, an ethical clearance was obtained from the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, the State Hospital Management Board, and Eye Clinic Molai (owned by EYC Missionary).

Sample and sampling techniques

The study followed Taryam et al. (2020) sampling approach in selecting about 25% from the population of visually impaired people in the state. The sample of visually impaired people was selected according to the division of the state into

three zones (Borno Central, Borno North, Borno South). However, most of the data were collected from the central and south zones due to challenge of insecurity. A cluster random sampling technique was employed. This approach involves dividing the population into clusters or strata, and random samples are drawn at each stage. The merit of this approach is that it maintains the random element in each stage, ensuring that each individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected.

Techniques of data analysis

All collected data were electronically captured with the aid of Open Data Kit (ODK) software on an Android phone to enable principal investigators to monitor the location and data collection process. ODK-captured data are sent to a central server from where the data is accessed, cleaned, organized and categorized for analysis. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics employing the measures of central tendency and measures of dispersion. Equally,

inferential statistics is used to test the hypothesis. In particular chi-square test was employed to examine the associations between engaged indicators. A combination of software such as SPSS and STATA were used for the descriptive statistics and hypotheses testing. The hypothesis tested is as follows:

H_0 : there is no direct and indirect monetary loss arising from cataract vision impairment in Borno state.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic information of the respondents

To measure the direct and non-direct medical loss arising from cataract vision impairment in Borno State. Table 1 below shows the demographic information of the vision impairment surveyed participants. Out of the 1200 questionnaires administered to vision impairment persons in the State, 1161 were retrieved, cleaned, and coded for the analysis.

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

		No. of observations= 1161	
Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender			
	Male	507	43.7
	Female	654	56.3
Age (years)			
	< 18 years	41	3.5
	18-27 years	61	5.3
	28-37 years	154	13.3
	38-47 years	198	17.1
	48-57 years	231	19.9
	58-67 years	256	22.0
	68-77 years	163	14.0
	> 78 years	57	4.9
Marital Status			
	Single	163	14.0
	Married	789	68.7
	Divorced	59	5.1
	Widowed	141	12.1
Level of Education			
	None	158	13.6
	Primary	111	9.6
	Secondary	348	30.0
	Tertiary	343	29.5
	Postgraduate	48	4.1
	Non-formal	153	13.2
Occupation Status			
	Civil servant	259	22.3
	Farming	206	17.7
	Trading	177	15.2

	Clergymen	20	1.7
	Unemployed/Retiree	155	13.4
	Housewife	164	14.1
	Others	180	15.5

Source: authors computation (2024)

The gender of the vision-impaired participants, as indicated in Table 1, revealed that the majority of them, 56.3% (654), were female, while 43.7% (507) were male. This indicates that vision impairment affects both genders. This supports the findings in the work of Rabiū et al. (2023), which is gender-sensitive, balanced, and inclusive for all genders. With regards to age, the majority of the cataract vision impaired patients surveyed were between the age ranges of 58 to 67 years, which accounts for 22% (256) of the participants. Within this age group, additional medical challenges requiring attention become more frequent. While 19.9% (231) were between the ages of 48 and 57 years. Similarly, 17.1% (198) were between 38 and 47 years, 14.0% (163) were between 68 and 77 years, 13.3% (154) were between 28 and 37 years, 5.3% (61) were between 18 and 27 years, 4.9% (57) were above 78 years, and 3.5% (41) were less than 18 years, respectively. This indicates that in most cases cataracts affect people between the ages of 40 and above. This is similar to the findings in the work of Bello et al. (2024), who found the average age of the vision patients was between the ages of 51-60 years. Although the reasons for this are not clear, it could be attributed to differences in study area, size of the sample, as well as change in life expectancy in Nigeria. Table 1 shows that a good proportion of the respondents were married, which accounts for 68.7% (789) of the vision-impaired patients in the study area, while 14.0% (163), 12.1% (141), and 5.1% (59) were single, widowed, and divorced, respectively. Also, Table 1 reveals that a good proportion of surveyed participants in the study area had secondary education, which accounts for 30.0% (348), while 29.5%

(343) of vision-impaired patients had tertiary education. Similarly, 13.6% (158), 13.2% (153), 9.6% (111), and 4.1% (48) had none, non-formal, primary, and postgraduate education qualifications, respectively. This shows that the majority of the surveyed vision-impaired patients had one form of formal education and indicates that participants are willing to take decisions that will help correct their vision. This is contrary to the findings in the work of Rabiū et al. (2023), who observed that the majority of the cataract patients did not attend any conventional schools.

In terms of occupation, a good proportion of the cataract vision impairment surveyed participants were civil servants, which account for 22.3% (259), while 17.7% (206) were farmers. Additionally, 15.5% (180) were in other occupations, 15.2% (177) were traders, 14.1% (164) were housewives, 13.4% (155) were unemployed and/or retired from services, and 1.7% (20) were clergymen, respectively.

Monthly income, number of years with impairment, and amount spent on cataract surgery

The monthly income status of the surveyed respondents, as indicated in table 2 below, shows that a good proportion were earning less than N20,000 a month, which accounts for 35.7% (414) of cataract vision impairment persons during the study period, while 22.4% (260) were receiving less than N40,000 monthly, 11.9% (138) were earning less than N60,000 monthly, 11.3% (131) were earning less than N80,000 monthly, 8.7% (101) were earning less than N100,000 monthly, and 10.1% (117) were earning above N100,000 monthly, respectively.

Table 2: Monthly income, number of years with impairment and amount spend on cataract surgery

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<20,000	414	35.7
20,001-40,000	260	22.4
40,001-60,000	138	11.9
60,001-80,000	131	11.3
80,001-100,000	101	8.7
> 100,000	117	10.1
Number of Years with Impairment		
<5	686	59.1
6-10	330	28.4
11-15	55	4.7
16-20	52	4.5
>20	38	3.3

Source: authors computation (2024)

With regards to the number of years with impairment, Table 2 shows that a greater proportion of the cataract vision patients were less than 5 years with the impairment, which accounts for 59.1% (686) of surveyed participants. 28.4% (330) were between 6 to 10 years with impairments, 4.7% (55) were between 11 to 15 years with the impairment, 4.5% (52) were between 16 to 20 years with the impairment, and 3.3% (38) were above 20 years with the impairment.

Eye medical centre/clinic normally attended in the state

Table 3 below shows the distribution of cataract vision impairment participants based on the medical center/eye clinic they visited in the state. About 47.5% of the respondents were attending general hospital Biu for medical treatment. While 31.7% were attending the eye clinic in Maiduguri for medication, 14.8% were attending the missionary eye clinic in Molai for medication, and 5.9% were attending the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital.

Table 3: Eye medical centre/clinic normally attend in the state?

Medical center normally attended in the state		Frequency	Percentage (%)
	UMTH	69	5.9
	Eye clinic Maiduguri	368	31.7
	EYN Missionary eye clinic Molai	172	14.8
	General Hospital Biu	552	47.5

Source: authors computation (2024)

Impact of economic burden arising from cataract vision impairment

The economic burden associated with cataract vision impairment is measured through direct medical expenditure and non-direct medical expenditure. Table 4 below presents the hypothesis tests between the number of years with impairment and the indicators of economic burden arising

from cataract vision impairment, using a chi-square method. To achieve inclusive outcomes, the direct medical expenditure was captured using indicators such as the amount incurred for diagnoses/laboratory tests, monthly expenditure on treatment/drugs, the amount spent on cataract surgery, and the amount spent per month on transportation to the hospital.

Table 4: Chi-square test of impact of economic burden (direct and non-direct medical expenditures) arising from cataract vision impairment

		Amount spend per month on transportation to the hospital vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		<5,000	5,001-10,000	10,001-15,000	15,001-20,000	>20,000	–	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of years with impairment	<5	506	131	2	20	8	–	686	169.35	0.0000
	6-10	184	124	15	3	3	–	329		
	11-15	23	20	6	4	2	–	55		
	16-20	18	17	6	3	8	–	52		
	>20	18	11	1	1	7	–	38		
Total		750	303	49	31	28	–	1161		
		Amount you incurred for diagnoses/laboratory tests vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		<10,000	10,001-20,000	20,001-30,000	30,001-40,000	40,000-50,000	>50,000	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of years with impairment	<5	466	138	39	25	11	7	686	32.54	0.0380
	6-10	144	132	28	14	8	3	329		
	11-15	14	21	10	1	8	1	55		
	16-20	14	14	3	6	5	10	52		
	>20	13	7	3	0	4	11	38		
Total		651	313	83	46	36	32	1161		
		Monthly Expenditure on Treatment/drug vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		<10,000	10,001-20,000	20,001-30,000	30,001-40,000	>40,000	–	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of years with impairment	<5	470	163	31	14	8	–	686	18.13	0.0030
	6-10	174	125	13	12	5	–	329		
	11-15	8	27	9	8	3	–	55		
	16-20	22	10	6	2	12	–	52		
	Total		686	329	55	38	52	38		

“Economic Cost of Vision Loss for Inclusive Development: The Direct and Indirect Perspectives”

		>20	21	7	0	2	8	–	38		
Total		696	332	59			338	–	1161		
		Amount spend on cataract surgery vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics		
		<50,000	50,001-80,000	80,001-100,000	>100,000	–	–	Total	χ^2	P-value	
No. of Years with Impairment	<5	532	64	40	50	–	–	686	26.16	0.0040	
	6-10	188	84	39	18	–	–	329			
	11-15	17	17	13	8	–	–	55			
	16-20	18	16	6	12	–	–	52			
	>20	20	5	2	11	–	–	38			
Total		775	187	100	99	–	–	1161			

Source: authors computation (2024)

As indicated in Table 4 above, the finding shows that all indicators of direct economic burden arising from cataract vision impairment were significantly associated with the number of years with impairment. This is proven by the probability values of amount spent per month on transportation to the hospital at a 1% level of significance, amount incurred for diagnoses/laboratory at a 5% level of significance, monthly expenditure on treatment/drug at a 1% level of significance, and amount spent on cataract surgery at a 1% level of significance. The implication of this finding is that as the number of years with impairment increases, the economic effect of vision impairment will be more pronounced on productivity and income. This corroborates with findings in the study of Rabiou et al. (2023), who found a

significant relationship between number of years with impairment and indicators of economic benefits and quality of life.

Indirect productivity cost

To examine whether cataract vision impairment has an impact on indirect productivity cost, Table 5 presents the hypothesis test using Chi-square. The indirect productivity cost was measured through indicators such as frequency of hospital visits for follow-ups, man-hours lost in each visit to see the eye doctor, ability to participate in the labour force, and other intangible costs associated with the cataract vision impairment.

Table 5: Chi-square test of impact of economic burden (indirect productivity cost) arising from cataract vision impairment

		Frequency of Hospital visit for follow-ups vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		weekly	Every two weeks	Monthly	Every two months	Anytime	–	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of years with impairment	<5	50	147	238	119	132	–	686	61.01	0.0000
	6-10	21	76	98	68	66	–	329		
	11-15	10	10	12	10	13	–	55		
	16-20	10	12	13	2	15	–	52		
	>20	10	14	7	0	7	–	38		
Total		101	260	368	199	233	–	1161		
		Man hour (s) loss in each visit to see the eye Doctor vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		< 1 Hour	2-3Hours	3-4 Hours	4-5 Hours	>5 Hours	–	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of years with impairment	<5	113	271	181	95	26	–	686	32.54	0.0380
	6-10	49	126	92	45	17	–	329		
	11-15	9	14	19	6	7	–	55		
	16-20	13	11	17	5	6	–	52		
	>20	7	19	6	3	3	–	38		
Total		191	441	316	154	59	–	1161		
		Have the cataract vision impairment hindered your ability to participate in the labour force vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		–	–	NO	–	YES	–	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of Years with Impairment	<5	–	–	316	–	686	–	686	18.13	0.0030
	6-10	–	–	114	–	215	–	329		
	11-15	–	–	15	–	40	–	55		
	16-20	–	–	19	–	33	–	52		

“Economic Cost of Vision Loss for Inclusive Development: The Direct and Indirect Perspectives”

	>20	—	—	15	—	23	—	38		
Total		—	—	479	—	682	—	1161		
		Other intangible costs associated with the cataract vision impairment vs Number of years with impairment							Test Statistics	
		—	—	NO	—	YES	—	Total	χ^2	P-value
No. of years with impairment	<5	—	—	321	—	364	—	686	26.16	0.0040
	6-10	—	—	112	—	216	—	329		
	11-15	—	—	14	—	41	—	55		
	16-20	—	—	16	—	36	—	52		
	>20	—	—	19	—	19	—	38		
Total		—	—	482	—	677	—	1161		

Source: authors computation (2024)

As indicated in Table 5 above, the finding shows that all indicators of indirect productivity cost arising from cataract vision impairment were significantly associated with the number of years with impairment. This is proven by the probability values of frequency of hospital visits for follow-ups at a 1% level of significance, man hour(s) lost in each visit to see the eye doctor at a 5% level of significance, ability to participate in the labour force at a 1% level of significance, and other intangible costs associated with the cataract vision impairment at a 1% level of significance. The implication of this finding is that as the number of years with impairment increases, the economic effect of vision impairment will be more pronounced on productivity. This is in tandem with findings in the work of Adio and Onua (2023), whose investigation acknowledged associated indirect costs. Moreover, a visually impaired individuals need to get someone else who is most likely to be economically productive to leave whatever he or she is doing and assist in getting them to the hospital. In addition, Bello et al. (2024) reported that with regards to indirect productivity cost per visit, the average loss of income for patients and their companions varies with their occupation. The higher the occupational class of the patients, the more their average productivity loss per visit. Whereas, unemployed group had the least average productivity loss per visit while the professional group had the highest productivity loss per visit.

CONCLUSION

The study assesses the direct and indirect economic loss arising from cataract-related blindness in Borno State. A survey was conducted on 1161 vision-impaired patients. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. For the inferential statistics, a chi-square test was employed to examine the associations between the employed variables. The results revealed that the majority (56.3%) of surveyed participants were female. With regards to age, the majority (22%) of the cataract vision impaired patients surveyed were between the age range of 58 to 67 years, and a good proportion of surveyed vision-impaired patients (68.7%) were married. Also, in terms of educational qualification, the majority (30.0%) of the surveyed participants in the study area had secondary education. In

terms of occupation, the majority of the respondents were civil servants (22.3%). The monthly income status of the surveyed respondents indicated that a good proportion were earning less than N20,000 a month (35.7%). With regards to the number of years with impairment, a greater proportion of the cataract vision patients were less than 5 years with the impairment (59.1%).

Moreover, the economic burden associated with cataract vision impairment is measured through direct medical expenditure and non-direct medical expenditure, and the results revealed that all indicators of direct economic burden (amount incurred for diagnoses/laboratory tests, monthly expenditure on treatment/drug, amount spent on cataract surgery, as well as the amount spent per month on transportation to the hospital) arising from cataract vision impairment were significantly associated with the number of years with impairment. The implication of this finding is that as the number of years with impairment increases, the economic effect of vision impairment will be more pronounced on productivity and income. Similarly, the finding shows that all indicators of indirect productivity cost (frequency of hospital visits for follow-ups, man-hours lost in each visit to see the eye doctor, ability to participate in the labour force, and other intangible costs associated with the cataract vision impairment) arising from cataract vision impairment were significantly associated with the number of years with impairment.

The study's results provide a persuasive case for policymakers, healthcare providers, and development stakeholders to prioritize cataract prevention and treatment as a critical component of public health strategies in Borno State. Moreover, when economic perspectives are integrated into healthcare planning, stakeholders can design sustainable interventions that can restore vision and also enhance economic productivity, thereby reducing the cycle of poverty. This research has contributed valuable evidence to the growing body of literature advocating for the inclusion of vision health in sustainable development frameworks, suggesting that addressing cataract-related vision impairment is both a health and economic imperative for the region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: This research is supported by TETFund NRF grant number TETF/ES/DR&D-CE/NRF2023/HSS/SDW/00069/VOL.1.

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